

Recommendations for Evaluating Expeditions and Adventure Travel in the Media

Ash Routen, BSc MSc PhD FRGS FI'26

Freelance Adventure Journalist, Leicestershire, United Kingdom

a.routen@gmail.com

www.ashrouten.com

Abstract

Adventure travel, expeditions, and exploration are more visible than ever across both traditional and digital media. However, how they are reported and represented is becoming increasingly problematic. As participation grows and media coverage expands, the line between noteworthy expeditions and personal or guided adventure travel has become blurred. This creates a challenge for editors, storytellers, and audiences alike. How do we recognise quality and genuine noteworthiness in an age defined by constant record claims and exaggerated narratives? This working paper does not propose a rigid framework. Instead, it offers guidance through a set of considerations designed to help journalists and audiences assess expeditions with greater clarity and consistency. At its core are five key factors: originality, distance, technical difficulty, remoteness, and independence. These are supported by secondary considerations including prior knowledge and purpose. This paper is intended as a starting point for further discussion, with the aim of refining these ideas through engagement with the wider adventure community.

1. The Need for Better Judgement in Adventure Media

The media plays a critical role in shaping how expeditions are understood and remembered. Increasingly, minor variations in expedition objectives are presented as major achievements, well-supported and guided journeys are framed as noteworthy, and tenuous record claims continue to grow^{1,2,3,4}. The problem is a lack of discernment by the media, and both mainstream and specialist adventure publications. There are no fixed rules however on what makes an expedition worthy of wider attention. Evaluation of an expedition or adventure is inherently subjective. However, without shared reference points, media reporting is inconsistent and overly influenced by narrative framing rather than the substance of the expedition itself.

2. Core Guidance

As an adventure writer, I've developed a loose set of guiding principles that I use when I decide whether a journey is genuinely interesting and cutting edge. These five elements form a foundation for judging expedition quality and importance. They are not rigid criteria, but together they offer a strong indication of significance. These principles [were first presented at an adventure festival](#) called 'Expedition Finse' in Norway in February 2026 and have since been refined following feedback at the festival and discussion with members of the adventure community. An example of a recent expedition which meets multiple key principles outlined below is one of the top ten ExplorersWeb expeditions of 2025: the first unsupported north-south crossing of Ellesmere Island in the Canadian Arctic⁵.

2.1 Originality

Originality is one of the clearest indicators. This includes journeys that follow routes that are rarely travelled or not travelled at all. It may involve a new line or bold variation (in climbing terms), a first ascent or new route/journey, or perhaps a reimagining of a long forgotten historic journey. The emphasis is not solely on being first but on whether the expedition adds something genuinely new and different or is particularly creative.

2.2 Distance

Distance matters, but only when understood in context. A long journey across benign terrain may be physically demanding, but it is not necessarily committing, or technically and logistically difficult. By contrast, a shorter journey in a hostile or technical environment may represent a far greater undertaking. For example, a 400km unsupported backpack in a remote range in the Yukon is a serious and difficult undertaking. A 400km backpack across a well-signposted hiking route in the European Alps is less so.

2.3 Technical Difficulty

Technical difficulty reflects the level of skill, judgement, and risk required to complete a journey. High technical difficulty includes travel over complex terrain such as heavily crevassed glaciers, sea ice, steep mixed alpine ground, or open ocean. These environments demand a high level of skill and constant decision making and carry higher consequence for error. The more technically demanding a journey is, the more it says about the team and their competence.

2.4 Remoteness

Remoteness also helps define the seriousness of an expedition. True remoteness is being days rather than hours from help. It is also about limited communication and limited options for support or rescue when things go wrong. In very remote environments, decisions carry more weight as mistakes cannot always be corrected. This fundamentally changes the character of a journey.

2.5 Independence

Independence relates to ownership of the expedition. An independent expedition is planned, organised, and executed by the team undertaking it. It is not guided, and decision making remains with the participants throughout. The team plans it, organises it, and executes it. Ownership of the expedition matters as it shapes both the experience and the outcome.

3. Secondary Considerations

Beyond the primary factors above, there are some additional elements that can help guide how an expedition should be understood.

3.1 Prior Knowledge and Information

On well-travelled objectives, there may be decades of accumulated knowledge on the route, conditions and required equipment. This reduces uncertainty, even when the objective remains physically or technically challenging. By contrast, when little or no prior information exists, uncertainty becomes a defining factor. The less known about an environment or objective, the greater the uncertainty, which is arguably a central component of adventure.

3.2 Purpose and Intent

Expeditions are driven by different motivations. These may include scientific research, personal challenge, cultural exploration, or storytelling. Purpose should not determine quality, but it provides context to the expedition objectives.

3.3 Narrative and Storytelling

For the media, the ability to tell a compelling story remains important. However, narrative should not be used to inflate the significance of an otherwise limited objective.

4. Conclusion

No expedition will excel across all areas outlined above, and it should not be expected to do so. A shorter expedition in an underexplored region may carry more significance than a long but heavily supported journey in a well-travelled region. A technically modest expedition with high uncertainty may be more meaningful than a technically difficult adventure on a very well-travelled route. However, what matters is not only what is done, but how it is communicated. What is highlighted and published by the media forms the cultural memory of adventure and exploration. In future, this working paper will require refinement through further involvement and engagement of the wider adventure community. This could include utilising stakeholder workshops or consensus building methodologies such as a Delphi exercise.

References

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